

Bacterial nanocellulose and its oxidized form as functional carriers for pomegranate peel extract: A sustainable approach to bioactive delivery

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ABSTRACT

This study explores bacterial nanocellulose (BNC) and its oxidized form (*o*-BNC) as carriers for pomegranate peel extract (PPE) intended for functional food applications. The TEMPO-mediated oxidation was used to introduce carboxylate groups to enhance the selectivity and efficiency of adsorbed active components from PPE. Structural and compositional analyses, including FTIR and HPLC, confirmed successful incorporation of PPE components, while FESEM provided an insight into the material's morphology. In vitro release studies of ellagic acid and punicalagin, showed more sustained release of the active compounds from *o*-BNC which is highly influenced by pH. Antioxidant activity was evaluated by DPPH and FRAP assays, while the α -glucosidase inhibition assay was used to assess the ability to slow carbohydrate digestion, which helps regulate blood sugar levels. The *o*-BNC-PPE formulation exhibited significantly higher antioxidant activity than BNC-PPE, attributed to its richer phenolic content. In hypoglycemic assays, *o*-BNC-PPE outperformed both BNC-PPE and the standard drug acarbose, showing greater α -glucosidase inhibitory activity (IC_{50} 1.41 μ g/mL for *o*-BNC-PPE vs. 29.1 μ g/mL for BNC-PPE and 156.6 μ g/mL for acarbose). Compared to unmodified BNC, a wider range of bioactive compounds was incorporated on *o*-BNC due to enhanced binding capacity and porosity, which translated into material stronger antioxidant activity, attributed to presence of additional phenolics like gallic acid and ellagitannins. These findings underscore the potential of BNC-based materials as carriers of natural bioactive compounds in functional foods, offering a sustainable approach to delivery of antioxidants and other health-promoting bioactive compounds through diet, while also supporting plant waste valorization.

1. Introduction

Bacterial nanocellulose (BNC) has garnered significant interest and extensive utilization in both research and industry as a sustainable organic, biodegradable biopolymer. This is largely attributed to its exceptional physical and chemical attributes, including its notable high surface area and water-holding capacity, low density, and impressive mechanical, thermal, and optical properties, alongside its biocompatibility (Ul-Islam et al., 2012; Ullah et al., 2021). Its remarkable adsorption capacity for biomolecules surpasses that of plant nanocellulose facilitating cell adhesion and proliferation (de Oliveira Barud et al., 2021; Kumar and Han, 2021; Samyn et al., 2023). Unlike plant-derived nanocellulose, BNC consists solely of cellulose without hemicellulose or lignin. BNC is synthesized through the cost-effective and

environmentally friendly production methods, such as fermentation processes, using low-cost or waste streams, which can easily be scaled, making it highly accessible (Rybychyn et al., 2021; Samyn et al., 2023).

Dense network of BNC fibers, known as a pellicle, on the surface of the liquid medium containing glucose or other suitable carbon source (Manan et al., 2022; Ul-Islam et al., 2020), is usually formed when representatives of *Komagataeibacter*, *Acetobacter*, *Brevibacterium*, or *Saracoccus* are incubated under static conditions (Ullah et al., 2015; Villarreal-Rueda et al., 2023). To obtain BNC at nanoscale dimensions of fibrils, this pellicle is collected, purified, and subjected to high-pressure homogenization or sonication (Reshmy et al., 2021; Xue, Mou and Xiao, 2017). The resulting nanoscale BNC is dried to remove excess water, yielding a three-dimensional, interconnected network of nanofibrils with widths between 70 and 140 nm (Ugrin et al., 2021).

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The versatility of BNC opens up promising avenues in medicine (Randhawa et al., 2022; Wahid et al., 2021), where it can serve as a biomaterial for tissue engineering (Choi et al., 2022), wound dressing (Kushwaha, Goswami and Kim, 2022), and drug delivery systems (Das, Ghosh and Sarkar, 2022; Huo et al., 2022). Its applications are particularly valuable in the food industry (Azarian, Junyusen and Sutapun, 2024; Dourado et al., 2016; Ludwicka, Kaczmarek and Białkowska, 2020; Ponjavic et al., 2023). In tropical regions like Vietnam, coconut water is used as an affordable carbohydrate source for producing BNC, yielding Nata de coco, a dilute hydrogel with high water retention and strength, and is consumed as a low-calorie, high-fiber food (Liu and Kong, 2021; Nguyen et al., 2023). Furthermore, BNC is also examined as the fat replacement and artificial meat (Azeredo et al., 2019). More recently, BNC showed health-promoting properties as a functional food ingredient (Wang et al., 2025), specifically as a blood glucose regulator. Furthermore, these materials find use in diverse fields such as electronics (Yu et al., 2021), and environmental remediation (Suárez-Avenidaño et al., 2022).

There are numerous methods to modify and to adjust the properties of BNC for the existing and new areas of application. Particularly interesting are the BNC-based nanocomposites with other components such as nanoparticles, polymers, and biomolecules for the deployment of materials with advanced new functionalities for a wide range of applications. These new BNC-based nanocomposites are created to obtain materials with good antimicrobial activity, antioxidant activity, electromagnetic properties, and catalytic activity, which are required for some specialized applications (Revin et al., 2022). BNC can acquire antibacterial properties through a straightforward oxidation process, resulting in the formation of carboxylate functional groups on its surface. These functional groups exhibit inherent antibacterial activity, which can be enhanced through electrostatic interaction with cationic or polycationic antibacterial agents (Shahriari-Khalaji et al., 2022).

Pomegranate (*Punica granatum* L., Punicaceae) is a widely used and grown fruit due to its pleasant taste and confirmed nutritional value (Ain et al., 2023; Al-Said, Opara and Al-Yahyai, 2009). After processing, fruit peel is usually treated as a waste and discarded (Ain et al., 2023). On the other hand, many studies showed that the fruit peel is a rich source of biologically active polyphenols such flavonoids, tannins and phenolic acids with punicalagin, punicalin, gallic and ellagic acids being the most abundant ones (Mo et al., 2022; Radan et al., 2024). Indeed, pomegranate fruit peel extract (PPE) has demonstrated a variety of biological activities due to its diverse chemical composition. These activities include anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, antioxidant, anti-diabetic, anti-neurodegenerative, anti-proliferative, immunomodulatory, and antiviral effects (Čolić et al., 2022; Minutolo et al., 2023; Sayed et al., 2022; Šavikin et al., 2018; Živković et al., 2021). Moreover, a double-blind, placebo-controlled randomized study, conducted by Grabež et al. (Grabež et al., 2020), showed beneficial effects of PPE capsules on blood pressure, levels of fatty acids and profile of plasma lipids in diabetes mellitus type-2 patients. Also, Grabež et al. (Grabež et al., 2020) demonstrated that the same PPE formulation had a positive effect on body composition and anthropometric measurements in overweight individuals with type-2 diabetes mellitus. Notably, the effects of PPE on blood pressure may not be limited to diabetes mellitus type-2 patients, as its anti-hypertensive action could have additional benefits, including anti-fibrotic activity, as suggested in a different study (Benedetti et al., 2024), pointing to the potential of PPE to support cardiovascular health in various populations. These results highlight the significant potential of PPE in preventing and treating various conditions and diseases, particularly chronic metabolic disorders. Importantly the ability to convert this plant-based waste material into value-added products supports the principles of food-waste reduction and sustainability. Therefore, this study aligns with several United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly SDG 3 (Good Health and Well-being), SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production) and SDG2 that aims to “end hunger, achieve food security and improved

nutrition and promote sustainable agriculture” (<https://sdgs.un.org/goals>). By utilizing BNC, the research encourages eco-friendly production and waste reduction, promoting responsible consumption (SDG 12). The incorporation of PPE further supports sustainability. BNC-based nutraceutical formulations for cardiovascular diseases, diabetes, and obesity contribute to health and well-being (SDG 3). Additionally, the development of these biocompatible, food-grade materials fosters sustainable industrial practices (SDG 9), offering an innovative solution to health and environmental challenges.

The objective of this research was to generate and evaluate a novel PPE nutraceutical formulation, with BNC and its oxidized form (*o*-BNC) as carriers for active agents. The oxidized BNC was produced by introducing a negative charge into the BNC structure, employing a well-known (2,2,6,6-Tetramethylpiperidin-1-yl)-oxyl (TEMPO)-mediated oxidation process on the porous morphology of BNC films. PPE was selected for the material functionalization due to its proven therapeutic effects in treating cardiovascular disorders, cancer, diabetes, and obesity. These novel formulations are anticipated to offer advantages over commercially available products, providing a broader range of health promoting activities with reduced toxicity and side effects relying on combination of food grade biocompatible cellulosic nanofibers and sustained release of the PPE bioactive compounds.

By utilizing environmentally friendly, waste-derived materials, this research introduces a cost-effective and scalable approach to developing bioactive carriers for chronic disease treatment. The novelty lies in the combination of BNC's biocompatibility and oxidative modification with PPE's proven health benefits, offering a unique solution for promoting health and reducing food waste.

2. Experimental part

2.1. Chemicals

2,2,6,6-Tetramethylpiperidine-1-oxyl (TEMPO,98%,) and citric acid were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Munich, Germany), sodium bromide (NaBr), sodium hypochlorite (NaClO) and sodium hydrogen phosphate heptahydrate ($\text{Na}_2\text{HPO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$) were purchased from ACROS Organics (Geel, Belgium). Ethanol (96 vol%) was purchased from Centrohem (Stara Pazova, Serbia), and hydrochloric acid (HCl, 36.2%) from Zorka Pharma (Šabac, Serbia). Phosphate buffer solution (PBS) was prepared using buffer tablets (pH 7.4, Genaxxon bioscience GmbH (Ulm, Germany). Potassium hydroxide (KOH) was purchased from Fisher Scientific (Leicestershire, UK). Glucose, yeast extract and bactopectone were purchased from Biolife (Milan, Italy). Ethanol, sodium carbonate anhydrous (Na_2CO_3) and phosphate buffer components (sodium-chloride and sodium-dihydrogen phosphate, anhydrous) were purchased from Centrohem (Stara Pazova, Serbia); hydrochloric acid, acarbose and *p*-nitrophenyl- α -D-glucopyranoside from Acros Organics (Geel, Belgium); 2,2-dyphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH), l-ascorbic acid, sodium acetate, 2,4,6-tris(2-pyridyl)-(S)-triazine (TPTZ), sodium acetate trihydrate, iron(III) chloride hexahydrate ($\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and iron(II) sulfate heptahydrate ($\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$) from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA).

2.2. Plant material and preparation of pomegranate peel extract

Mature pomegranate fruits were collected during November 2023 in the village Do (Bosnia and Herzegovina) at the natural locality. According to our previous procedure (Radan et al., 2024), peel was separated manually, shredded and air-dried at room temperature during six days. Further, it was ground using laboratory mill and sieved to obtain 0.75 to 2.00 mm particles (pH Yug. V). Plant material was previously deposited in Botanical Garden “Jevremovac”, University of Belgrade (voucher specimen No. BEOU 17742).

PPE was obtained according to our previous procedure (Radan et al., 2024). Briefly, pomegranate peel was extracted with 50% ethanol

(EtOH), dry-to-solvent ratio of 1:5, using double percolation method. Ethanol was evaporated using a vacuum evaporator and residual liquid was dried using spray dryer LabtexESDTi (Huddersfield, UK) without coating material.

2.3. BNC growth

BNC was synthesized through the cultivation of the *Komagataeibacter medellinensis* ID13488 strain (CECT 8140 from the Spanish Type Culture Collection) in a Hestrin Schramm medium (HS) (20 g/L of 50% glucose solution, 5.0 g/L peptone, 5.0 g/L yeast extract, 2.5 g/L Na₂HPO₄, and 1.15 g/L citric acid). BNC growth was performed under static conditions and pH value was set to 4.5 by adding concentrated HCl. Cultures were allowed to incubate for 14 days at 30 °C. Subsequently, BNC was harvested, treated with potassium hydroxide (KOH, 5 wt%) and then washed with deionized H₂O until neutral pH was reached. Obtained BNC was freeze-dried (using Martin Christ Alpha 1–2 Ldplus (Osterode am Harz, Germany) at –50 °C for 24 h) to produce a sponge-like, white, porous material. The BNC yield was calculated using the following Eq. (1):

$$\text{Yield (mg / mL)} = m_{\text{BNC}} / V_{\text{culture medium}} \quad (1)$$

where the m_{BNC} is dry weight of purified BNC expressed per 1 mL of HS medium.

2.4. TEMPO oxidation of BNC

A modified version of the previously reported TEMPO oxidation method (Shahriari-Khalaji et al., 2022) was used to alter the structure of BNC. First, freeze-dried BNC material (1.0 g) was suspended in 300 mL of water, using a kitchen blender (Gorenje blender BN 1200 AL), followed by the addition of NaBr (0.5 g), TEMPO (40.0 mg), and 22.5 mL of NaClO solution (5% of active chlorine) (15 mmol/g cellulose) to the reaction mixture. The reaction mixture was stirred for 6 h at room temperature. After 6 h, the reaction was stopped by adding 50 mL of ethanol, and the obtained *o*-BNC was washed with 1 L of deionized H₂O to remove the unreacted NaClO, unbonded residuals and ethanol. Washed *o*-BNC was freeze dried, resulting in the sponge-like *o*-BNC with a yield of 0.67 g (67%).

2.5. Incorporation of PPE

PPE was incorporated into BNC and TEMPO-oxidized BNC (*o*-BNC) applying the previously used procedure (Ponjavic et al., 2023) with slight adaptations: 0.60 g of freeze-dried BNC or (*o*-BNC) was suspended in 110 mL of deionized H₂O using a kitchen blender. PPE (90.0 mg dissolved in 5 mL of deionized H₂O, targeted amount of PPE was 15 wt% calculated to BNC or *o*-BNC) was added to the BNC or (*o*-BNC) suspension, and shaken (180 rpm) at 37 °C for 24 h. After the predetermined period, the suspension sludge was filtered to remove the solvent, and placed in a deep-freezer at –70 °C for 4 h followed by freeze-drying. Obtained freeze-dried materials had a yellowish-brown color for BNC, with a yield of 0.67 g (97%), and pale-yellow color for *o*-BNC, with a yield of 0.65 g (94%).

2.5.1. Efficiency of incorporation of PPE

The effectiveness of PPE incorporation as an active compound was examined using UV–VIS spectroscopy (UV–ViS, UV-1900i spectrophotometer, SHIMADZU, Tokyo, Japan) at a wavelength of 370 nm. The standard method for determining the efficiency of adsorption ($EA\%$) via UV–ViS spectroscopy involves measuring the concentration of PPE before and after incorporation in the material. To facilitate this, a calibration curve of PPE in water was established, measuring concentrations ranging from 50 to 500 ppm at a wavelength of $\lambda = 370$ nm. Equation of calibration curve was $y = 0.0025x + 0.0923$ ($R^2 = 0.9948$).

2.6. Characterization of prepared films

2.6.1. ATR–Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) analysis

FTIR was used for structural characterization of BNC, *o*-BNC and PPE, as well as for detecting potential interactions between BNC (*o*-BNC) and the incorporated PPE. The samples underwent analysis using an IR-Affinity spectrophotometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, NICOLET iS10, Waltham, MA, USA) in attenuated total reflection (ATR) mode. Measurements were conducted within the predefined wavenumber range of 4000 to 400 cm^{–1}, at room temperature with a resolution of 4 cm^{–1}, employing a fixed number of scans set at 32.

2.6.2. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) analysis

Surface morphology of BNC and *o*-BNC samples, before and after the incorporation of the active compound, was inspected by SEM analysis (in triplicates), in order to determine the potential morphological alterations induced by the presence of the PPE. Examination was performed utilizing JEOL JSM-6390LV SEM (JEOL USA Inc., Peabody, MA, USA) with an accelerating voltage of 10 kV. Prior to recordings, samples were fixed on a holder using carbon tape, sputtered with gold (using BAL-TEC SCD 005, Wetter (Ruhr), Germany) for 30 min and lyophilized in a vacuum chamber (VC 50 SalvisLab Vacucenter, Rotkreuz, Switzerland).

2.6.3. Porosity and wettability tests of BNC and *o*-BNC

The porosity of the pure and *o*-BNC samples was determined by utilizing the ethanol displacement technique, described by Jain et al. (Jain et al., 2024). Initially, the dry weight of samples (W_0) sized at 4.0 cm x 1.5 cm x 0.5 cm was measured, and their volumes (V) were computed. Subsequently, the samples were submerged in ethanol (99.5%) at room temperature until saturation, followed by weighing (W_1) after excess ethanol removal. Porosity was then calculated using the following Eq. (2):

$$\text{Porosity (\%)} = (W_1 - W_0) / (\rho \times V) \times 100 \quad (2)$$

where ρ is the density of ethanol (0.79 g/cm³) used as the immersing medium.

2.6.4. Swelling ratio

To ascertain the percentage of fluid absorption, dry samples measuring 6.0 mm in diameter and 1.5 mm in height were submerged in PBS solution. Before immersion, the initial dry weight of the sample (W_0) was noted. Subsequently, the samples were immersed in PBS solution, at room temperature, and the PBS uptake was measured over time. After the removal of the excess of PBS solution from the surface with filter paper, the weight of the wet sample (W_1) was measured and the PBS uptake was assessed as following (3).

$$\text{PBS Uptake (\%)} = (W_1 - W_0) / W_0 \times 100 \quad (3)$$

2.7. HPLC analysis of individual compounds

HPLC analysis was done according to our previous procedure (Radan et al., 2024). Briefly, Agilent 1260 RR HPLC apparatus (Agilent, Waldbronn, Germany) equipped with 190–550 nm diode-array detector and reverse-phase analytical column Zorbax SB-C18 (Agilent) 150 mm x 4.6 mm i.d; 5 μ m was used. Temperature of the column was maintained at 25 °C and the injection volume was 3 μ L. Mobile phase A consisted of 1% (v/v) solution of orthophosphoric acid in water while mobile phase B was acetonitrile. Gradient elution was performed according to the following scheme: 0–5 min, 98–90%A; 5–15 min, 90% A; 15–20 min, 90–85% A; 20–25 min, 85–70% A; 25–30 min, 70–40% A; 30–34 min, 40–0% A and flow rate was 1 mL/min. Detection was done on 260, 280, 320, 360, and 380 nm, while the identification of the individual compounds was achieved by comparison with the UV spectra and the retention time of authentic standard compounds (punicalin,

punicalagin, ellagic and gallic acids). Calibration curves were used to calculate the amounts of each compound. The obtained results were presented as milligrams per gram of dry weight (mg/g DW).

2.8. In vitro release study

The release profiles of ellagic acid (marker compound) and punicalagin from dry pomegranate peel extract, BNC and *o*-BNC were investigated in two mediums – 0.1 M HCl (pH 1.2) and phosphate buffer (pH 7.4). The test was conducted in the beakers placed in the water bath (Erweka DT70, Erweka, Langen, Germany) at 100 rpm during the period of 60 min at 37 ± 1 °C. Namely, samples were immersed in medium and covered by cotton gauze in order to prevent flotation of *o*-BNC-PPE and BNC-PPE powders. The small volumes (roughly 1 mL) of medium were drawn and filtrated at fixed time intervals (1, 5, 15, 30 and 60 min) and immediately replaced with a fresh medium. The concentrations of dissolved marker compounds in collected samples were determined by HPLC (Section 2.7). The study was performed in triplicate and the results are presented as the mean value \pm standard deviation (S.D.). The comparison of release profiles was performed by calculating the similarity factor (f_2), according to Eq. (4). A value f_2 lower than 50 implies that the profiles are significantly different, while the f_2 value of 50 corresponds to an average difference of 10% between profiles.

$$f_2 = 50 \times \log \left\{ \left[1 + \frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^t (R_t - T_t)^2 \right]^{-0.5} \times 100 \right\} \quad (4)$$

where, n is the number of dissolution sampling times, R_t and T_t are the ellagic acid release percentage at each time for the reference and test sample, respectively.

Furthermore, obtained data of ellagic release was fitted into zero-order, first-order, Higuchi, and Korsmeyer–Peppas models (Table 1). The model with the highest correlation coefficient (R^2) was suggested as the model that describes release kinetics through the most realistic mechanism.

2.9. Antioxidant activity

2.9.1. DPPH assay

The ability of pomegranate BNC and *o*-BNC formulations to neutralize 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) radicals was evaluated using the colorimetric assay (Kolundžić et al., 2016). After preparation of serial dilutions of pomegranate formulations in 50% ethanol (2 mL), to each of them was added 0.5 mM DPPH solution in ethanol (0.5 mL), strongly shaken, and incubated for 30 min in the dark place. The absorbance was measured at 517 nm, whereby ethanol was used as a blank. The percentage of DPPH radicals' inhibition was calculated using the estimation (5):

Table 1

Mathematical models applied for the prediction of ellagic acid release kinetics from BNC-PPE and *o*-BNC-PPE sample.

Mathematical model	Equation	Parameter
Zero-order	$F = M_t/M_\infty = K_0 \cdot t$	K_0 - kinetic constant; t - time period of release of the active compound.
First-order	$F = M_t/M_\infty = 100[1 - \text{Exp}(-K_1 \cdot t)]$	K_1 - kinetic constant; t - time period of release of the active compound.
Higuchi model	$F = M_t/M_\infty = K_H \cdot t^{1/2}$	K_H - Higuchi dissolution constant; t - time period of release of the active compound.
Korsmeyer-Peppas	$F = M_t/M_\infty = K_p \cdot t^n$	K_p - kinetic constant; t - time period of release of the active compound; n - release exponent indicating the mechanism of active compound release.

F - fraction of the dissolved active compound at time t .

$$\text{Inhibition (\%)} = [(A_c - A_s) / A_c] \times 100 \quad (5)$$

where A_c is the absorbance of the control (50% ethanol was used instead of pomegranate formulations), and A_s is the absorbance of the sample. The results were expressed as IC_{50} values ($\mu\text{g/mL}$). l-ascorbic acid was used as positive control.

2.9.2. FRAP assay

Assessment of pomegranate BNC and *o*-BNC formulations total antioxidant capacity (reduction of ferric (Fe^{3+}) to ferrous (Fe^{2+}) ion) was performed according to the Benzie and Strain method (Benzie and Strain, 1996), with slight modifications. FRAP reagent consisted of TPTZ solution (10 mmol/L of 2,4,6-tripyridil-s-triazine in 40 mmol/L of hydrochloric acid), $\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ solution (20 mmol/L in distilled water) and acetate buffer (300 mmol/L, pH 3.6), which were mixed in the ratio 10:1:1 (v/v/v). The optimal concentration of pomegranate formulations was prepared in 50% ethanol (0.1 mL), to each of them was added FRAP reagent (3 mL), and obtained mixtures were left for 30 min at 37 °C. The absorbance was measured at 593 nm. The blank represented FRAP reagent mixed with 50% ethanol. Water solutions of $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (200 – 1000 $\mu\text{mol/L}$) were used for the construction of calibration curve ($y = 0.0209x + 0.0015$; $R^2 = 0.9976$). The FRAP-value was expressed as mmol Fe^{2+}/g of dry formulation. l-ascorbic acid was used as positive control.

2.10. α -Glucosidase inhibition assay

α -Glucosidase inhibitory activity of pomegranate BNC and *o*-BNC formulations was estimated by following the procedure described by Indrianingsih et al. (Indrianingsih, Tachibana and Itoh, 2015), with slight modifications. Briefly, solutions of the formulations at different concentrations (30 μL) were mixed with the substrate, *p*-nitrophenyl- α -D-glucopyranoside solution (0.6 mg/mL; 250 μL), and phosphate buffer (pH 6.9; 470 μL), pre-incubated for 5 min in water bath (37 °C), and then α -glucosidase solution (type I, ≥ 10 units/mg solid; 250 μL) was added, and further incubated for 15 min. To stop the reaction, 0.2 M Na_2CO_3 solution (1000 μL) was used. The absorbance was measured at 400 nm. The blank contained phosphate buffer instead of the enzyme solution. The percentage inhibition of α -glucosidase activity was calculated using the estimation (6):

$$(\%) \text{Inhibition} = [(A_c - A_s) / A_c] \times 100 \quad (6)$$

where A_c is the absorbance of the control (the phosphate buffer was used instead of formulation solution) and A_s is the absorbance of the sample. The results were expressed as IC_{50} values ($\mu\text{g/mL}$). Acarbose was used as positive control.

The spectrophotometric readings were conducted on Cary 3500 Multicell UV-Vis Spectrophotometer (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA).

2.11. Statistical analysis

The experimental data are presented as the mean values \pm standard deviation at three repeats. Statistical analyses of the obtained results were done using Statistica software version 5.0 (StatSoft Co., Tulsa, OK, USA). Significances of differences between samples were analyzed by Tukey's test. Differences at $p < 0.05$ were considered significant.

3. Results and discussion

This study was focused on functionalization and activation of BNC with the final aim to modulate the incorporation and release of PPE active compounds adsorbed into the pristine and the modified BNC, in order to open the applicative potential of produced BNCs-PPE as a functional food (Scheme 1).

PPE was incorporated into BNC and *o*-BNC suspensions through the

Scheme 1. Conceptualization of the presented study: oxidation of BNC and the production of BNC-PPE and *o*-BNC-PPE.

simple adsorption from PPE solution, resulting in 97% yield for BNC-PPE and 94% yield for *o*-BNC-PPE, measured by gravimetric method. The assessed adsorption efficiency of PPE was $53.3 \pm 2.0\%$ for *o*-BNC, while unmodified BNC with $65.7 \pm 1.7\%$ adsorbed about 20% more (Table 2). The content of the most prominent bioactive compounds in pomegranate peel extract, *o*-BNC-PPE, and BNC-PPE samples, was determined by the HPLC method (Table 2, Figure S1). Ellagitannins (punicalagin and punicalin), ellagic acid and gallic acid were identified in pomegranate peel extract, as well as in the *o*-BNC-PPE sample. On the other hand, ellagic acid was the only bioactive compound from the monitored ones found in the BNC-PPE sample. This result suggested that oxidative functionalization of BNC has increased adsorption of the wider range of bioactive compounds. Ellagic acid was further selected as a marker compound as it was the only bioactive compound found in comparable amounts in both *o*-BNC-PPE and BNC-PPE samples (Table 2). Furthermore, ellagic acid is one of the most valuable bioactive compounds in the pomegranate peel extract because of its many beneficial biological activities including anti-inflammatory, anti-mutagenic, anti-carcinogenic and neuroprotective activity (Verotta et al., 2018; Zuccari et al., 2020). During the digestion, the ellagic acid is transformed into urolithins that are pleiotropic agents by the action of gut microbiota (García-Villalba et al., 2022). However, the bioavailability of ellagic acid is low, mostly due to its poor water solubility ($9.7 \mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) and limited permeability (apparent permeability coefficient = $0.13 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm/s}$) (Zuccari et al., 2020). Additionally, the half-life of ellagic acid is short (Kang et al., 2016). Therefore, an efficient incorporation of the PPE and especially ellagic acid into both forms of BNC has potential to overcome these issues by enabling the controlled release of ellagic acid and other bioactive compounds.

Table 2
Efficiency of adsorption and the amount of individual compounds in BNC and *o*-BNC.

Sample	Efficiency of adsorption, %	Punicalagin, mg/g	Punicalin, mg/g	Ellagic acid, mg/g	Gallic acid, mg/g
BNC	65.7 ± 1.7	ND	ND	1.65 ± 0.03	ND
<i>o</i> -BNC	53.3 ± 2.0	15.2 ± 0.75	6.44 ± 0.32	1.78 ± 0.04	0.01 ± 0.00

3.1. FTIR analysis

FTIR spectra were taken to confirm the oxidation of BNC by TEMPO and the successful incorporation of PPE onto both BNC and *o*-BNC (Fig. 1).

Overall, TEMPO-mediated oxidation is expected to facilitate the oxidation of primary -OH functional groups, located on each of the β -D-glucopyranose monomers of BNC, to anionic and more hydrophilic carboxylate groups ($-\text{COO}^-$). Indeed, distinct, robust peak appears at 3342 cm^{-1} , attributed to the stretching vibrations of hydrogen-bonded hydroxyl groups, which is characteristic of pure BNC (Gaulke et al., 2023). Additionally, two broad peaks stemming from aliphatic C—H stretching are observed at 2920 and 2859 cm^{-1} . The presence of peaks at 1162 and 1107 cm^{-1} suggests asymmetric vibrations from the epoxide ring C—O—C stretching, while a peak at 1055 cm^{-1} corresponds to the C—O stretching vibration. Notably, strong peaks from the carbonyl group of the amide group I, residual proteins present in pure BNC, are evident at 1653 and 1629 cm^{-1} (Dima et al., 2017). This assertion is reinforced by the reduction or disappearance of these peaks in the spectrum of oxidized BNC, which underwent additional purification. The increased presence of carboxylate ions leads to mutual repulsion, disrupting hydrogen bonds within the BNC molecules. Consequently, the intensity of the vibration frequency of the hydroxyl groups on the BNC molecules increases. Furthermore, *o*-BNC displays a distinctive peak at 1735 cm^{-1} corresponding to the $-\text{C}=\text{O}$ stretching of the carboxylate group, indicating successful TEMPO-mediated oxidation (Cui et al., 2014).

In the spectrum of PPE, a broad peak ranging from 3500 to 3000 cm^{-1} arises from the -OH group of phenols, accompanied by strong peaks at 1715 and 1589 cm^{-1} , likely originating from carbonyl stretching of carboxylic groups and $-\text{C}=\text{C}$ aromatic stretching, respectively (Kokabi and Nejad Ebrahimi, 2021). Incorporation of PPE introduces additional bands in the FTIR spectrum of BNC, manifesting as a peak at 1582 cm^{-1} . Notably, the spectrum of *o*-BNC-PPE exhibits two extra peaks attributable to PPE compared to pure oxidized BNC spectrum, observed at 1720 and 1603 cm^{-1} (Fig. 1). The broad PPE absorption peak at 3250 cm^{-1} , most likely from the intramolecular hydrogen bonding, is missing in both BNC-PPE and *o*-BNC-PPE spectra (Hishikawa, Togawa and Kondo, 2017). BNC hydroxyl groups most likely form new H-bonds with the hydrophilic groups of PPE, thus disrupting preexisting intramolecular H-bonds. This suggests altered adsorption properties of *o*-BNC due to the presence of carboxylate groups, enabling interactions with a broader range of PPE components compared to unmodified BNC as observed by the assessment of active compounds (Table 2).

Fig. 1. FTIR analysis of pristine BNC samples, BNCs containing pomegranate peel extract and pure PPE.

3.2. Morphological characterization

The surface characteristics of BNC and *o*-BNC, both before and after the addition of PPE, were examined using FESEM (Fig. 2). The images reveal that the surface of pure freeze-dried BNC exhibits a distinct fibrous 3D network structure, with random distribution of fibrils, and interconnected porous morphology of the fibers, as previously observed (Gaulke et al., 2023). The type of three-dimensional structure in the BNC membranes allows for high porosity and a substantial surface area, making them well-suited for incorporation and immobilization of diverse active agents (Ataide et al., 2017). TEMPO-mediated oxidation of BNC impacted the structure of the 3D network, resulting in higher porosity (Fig. 2, third column). The carboxylate functional group of the *o*-BNC exhibits greater hydrophilicity, compared to the hydroxyl group in the pure BNC, leading to repulsive interactions among oxidized microfibrils (Cañas-Gutiérrez et al., 2020; Chen et al., 2022).

After incorporation of PPE onto both BNC and *o*-BNC, PPE particles were clearly visible and bonded to the carrier microfibrils. While the three-dimensional fibrillary network on the BNC-PPE surface remained

akin to that of pure BNC, the overall morphology experienced only minor modifications due to the aggregation of PPE particles on the microfibrils, evident in the provided BNC-PPE micrographs. The PPE particles formed clusters of irregular shapes and sizes on the BNC surface through intermolecular interactions, consequently influencing the formation of hydrogen bonds among BNC microfibrils. Conversely, the surface of *o*-BNC-PPE exhibited a different trend, characterized by lower amounts of smaller PPE particles adhering to the microfibrils. This observation is in line with previous observations that the presence of carboxylate functional groups on the *o*-BNC surface may lead to more selective bonding interactions with the active compounds of PPE (Table 2, Fig. 1).

3.3. PBS uptake and porosity

Upon immersion in a PBS solution, both BNC and *o*-BNC samples exhibited rapid swelling, reaching equilibrium swelling ratio within an hour. Both tested samples demonstrated considerable absorption of PBS after 1 h, measuring at $2674.4 \pm 25.9\%$ for BNC-PPE and $2988.6 \pm$

Fig. 2. SEM analysis micrographs of BNC, *o*-BNC, BNC-PPE and *o*-BNC-PPE samples using different magnification ($250 \times$ and $50k \times$).

19.1% for *o*-BNC-PPE, respectively. The higher swelling rate observed in *o*-BNC-PPE could be attributed to its more hydrophilic nature, characterized by microfibrils containing carboxylate functional groups.

Using the ethanol displacement porosity measurement, it was determined the porosity to be $96.32 \pm 3.61\%$ for *o*-BNC-PPE sample and $83.56 \pm 2.91\%$ for the BNC-PPE samples. This finding is consistent with the observations from FESEM micrographs, which indicate higher porosity in the *o*-BNC-PPE samples. Notably, both samples exhibit significantly higher porosity than the original BNC films, which had a porosity of $50.26 \pm 1.43\%$ (Jain et al., 2024).

3.4. PPE release in different mediums

The release of ellagic acid from BNC-PPE and *o*-BNC-PPE samples was monitored in different media (pH 1.2 and 7.4) relevant for gastric and intestinal conditions (Fig. 3a). Release of ellagic acid was slower under acidic conditions from both samples, as was expected since the solubility of ellagic acid increases with pH (Zuccari et al., 2020). Furthermore, *o*-BNC-PPE sample contains ellagitannins which are quite resistant to acid hydrolysis (pH 1.2 and pH 4.5), while at pH 7.4 influence of hydrolysis is evident according to the previous reports (García-Villalba et al., 2022), as well as our findings. Under acidic conditions, the release of ellagic acid was slower from the *o*-BNC-PPE than from the BNC-PPE sample. Similarity factor f_2 (47.60) indicated

that the release profiles of ellagic acid from *o*-BNC-PPE and BNC-PPE samples were significantly different at pH 1.2. This result is consistent with previous findings since it was also shown that natural product actinomycin release was slower from oxidized than from pure BNC, due to enhanced adsorption and stronger interaction between oxidized carrier and active compound (Zimowska et al., 2024). Moreover, considering the high porosity of BNC-PPE and *o*-BNC-PPE samples flotation of obtained formulations in the stomach could be expected. It was reported previously that ellagic acid was primarily absorbed from the stomach and the upper region of the small intestine (Kang et al., 2016), indicating that prolonged release in the stomach could improve the bioavailability of ellagic acid.

The release profile of ellagic acid from the *o*-BNC-PPE sample and BNC-PPE have similar trends at pH 7.4 ($f_2 = 60.22$). However, it should be emphasized that the release profile of ellagic acid from *o*-BNC-PPE at pH 7.4 was influenced by the presence of other compounds, i.e. ellagitannins punicalagin and punicalin, which are highly hydrolysable under neutral or slightly alkaline pH (Table S1). On the other hand, ellagic acid was the only bioactive compound found in the BNC sample and consequently release profile of ellagic acid from BNC-PPE was not influenced by the ellagitannins hydrolysis.

The correlation coefficients (R^2) obtained after the adjustment of ellagic acid release profile from *o*-BNC-PPE and BNC-PPE at pH 1.2 and 7.4 to mathematical models (zero-order, first-order, Higuchi, and

Fig. 3. Release of: a) ellagic acid and b) punicalagin from *o*-BNC-PPE samples at pH 1.2 and 7.4.

Korsmeyer-Peppas) are presented in Table 3. The highest correlation coefficients for ellagic acid release from the o-BNC-PPE sample at pH 1.2 were observed for the first-order and Korsmeyer-Peppas models, while in all other cases, the release followed the Korsmeyer-Peppas model. Results showed that ellagic acid was released following the Fickian diffusion mechanism since the release exponent (n) was below 0.45 from both samples (Table 3). The same trend was reported in the case of the release of cyanidin-3-O-rutinoside as well as actinomycin from BNC (Ponjavic et al., 2023; Zimowska et al., 2024).

In addition to ellagic acid, the release of punicalagin from o-BNC-PPE sample was also investigated. Punicalagin is abundant component of pomegranate peel but it needs to be transformed into simpler bioactive metabolites to elicit bioactivity (Caballero et al., 2022). Hydrolysis of punicalagin in the stomach and intestine yields ellagic acid (Fig. 4) (Hering et al., 2021).

As shown in Fig. 3b, the release profile of punicalagin was biphasic at a pH of 1.2. Namely, burst release of punicalagin was observed in the first 15 min, after which a sustained release was achieved. On the other hand, it was evident that its hydrolysis occurred at pH 7.4, indicating that the higher chemical stability of punicalagin in an acidic environment is confirmed. Wang et al. (Wang et al., 2023) also showed that the amount of punicalagin from pomegranate peel increased after gastric digestion while it decreased after intestinal digestion, becoming undetectable.

3.5. Antioxidant and hypoglycemic activities

Numerous pharmacological studies have found that pomegranate peel exhibits a wide range of activities, such as antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, apoptotic, hypoglycemic and hypolipemic, which could be particularly useful in the prevention or mitigation of cardiovascular disorders and cancer, as well as diabetes and obesity (Azmat et al., 2024; Grabez et al., 2020; Grabež et al., 2020; Sayed et al., 2022). Due to various outstanding properties, including high surface area, biocompatibility and biodegradability, bacterial nanocellulose is recognized as a suitable carrier for active substances and natural products (Varghese et al., 2023). Aiming to obtaining natural material with a promising nutraceutical or medicinal potential, BNC and o-BNC pomegranate peel extract incorporated formulations (BNC-PPE and o-BNC-PPE, respectively) were evaluated in terms of antioxidant and hypoglycemic activities.

3.5.1. Antioxidant activity

The antioxidant potential of BNC-PPE and o-BNC-PPE formulations was evaluated by measuring their free radical scavenging activities (DPPH) and reducing abilities (FRAP). As presented in Fig. 5, both formulations expressed valuable antioxidant activities. Taking into account the results of both assays, the statistically significant higher antioxidant activity was measured for o-BNC-PPE formulation, which can be attributed to the differences in their chemical composition. Namely, ellagic acid was identified as the only active principle of BNC

pomegranate formulation, while gallic acid and ellagitannins (punicalagin and punicalin), along with ellagic acid, were revealed as the most dominant representatives of secondary metabolites in o-BNC-PPE formulation. These phytochemicals are characterized by the presence of conjugated aromatic systems and multiple phenolic groups, which enable them to act as antioxidants (Dai and Mumper, 2010). As the o-BNC-PPE sample was characterized by the presence of all four typical pomegranate phenolic compounds it showed higher antioxidant activity than the BNC-PPE sample. However, the antioxidant activity of l-ascorbic acid (DPPH – IC_{50} 4.45 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$; FRAP value – 15.94 mmol Fe^{2+}/g) was higher than that of our samples. Previous findings suggested strong DPPH antioxidant activity of pomegranate peel extracts, with IC_{50} values ranging from 12.49 to 6.12 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ (Benchagra et al., 2021; Dadwal et al., 2017). In our previous study, PPE showed IC_{50} value of 6.51 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ in DPPH test (Radan et al., 2024).

3.5.2. Hypoglycemic activity

Given that *diabetes mellitus* is a global metabolic disorder, related to impaired glucose metabolism and chronic hyperglycemia, examination of natural products and herbal preparations as potential hypoglycemic agents is on the rise (Radan et al., 2024). One of the proposed therapeutic approaches in diabetes management is the suppression of post-prandial hyperglycemia by inhibiting carbohydrate-digesting enzymes, α -amylase and α -glucosidase (Radan et al., 2024; Šavikin et al., 2018). In this study, the hypoglycemic potential of BNC-PPE and o-BNC-PPE formulations was evaluated through an in vitro analysis of anti- α -glucosidase activity. As was the case in the antioxidant assays, the o-BNC-PPE formulation (IC_{50} 1.41 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) expressed stronger α -glucosidase inhibitory activity in comparison to the BNC-PPE formulation (IC_{50} 29.09 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$). However, the results indicated that both formulations are appreciable more effective in inhibition of α -glucosidase than standard drug acarbose, known α -glucosidase inhibitor (IC_{50} 156.64 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$). According to the literature data, the hypoglycemic activity of pomegranate peel extracts has been established in many in vitro, animal and human studies (Grabez et al., 2020; Okumuş and Bakkalbaşı, 2021; Radan et al., 2024). When it comes to possible contributors to demonstrated hypoglycemic activity, ellagitannins (punicalagin and punicalin) and free ellagic acid were identified as the most important α -glucosidase inhibitors (Bellesia, Verzelloni and Tagliuzucchi, 2015).

The oxidized BNC formulation exhibited superior performance in adsorbing and releasing active components, with higher antioxidant activity and a more potent hypoglycemic effect compared to the pristine BNC formulation. Notably, both formulations showed greater α -glucosidase inhibitory activity, compared to the standard drug acarbose, suggesting their potential as natural alternatives in supporting management of diabetes and impaired glucose tolerance.

However, despite the promising results, some of the limitations of this study, including the need for further in vivo validation to confirm the efficacy and bioavailability of these formulations in clinical settings, have been recognized. Additionally, scalability and long-term stability of these BNC-based materials require further investigation. Ongoing research could focus on optimizing the production processes, enhancing the bioavailability of bioactive compounds, and exploring additional therapeutic applications of BNC-PPE formulations in functional foods and nutraceuticals.

4. Conclusion

Two novel PPE formulations based on BNC have been successfully generated. Structural analysis confirmed the effective oxidation of BNC, introducing carboxylate groups on the nanocellulose surface. This modification also increased porosity by inducing repulsion between negatively charged fibrils. Porosity values of composite materials were high (96.32% for o-BNC-PPE and 83.56% for BNC-PPE), significantly surpassing the original BNC film's 50.26%. Oxidized analogue of BNC appeared more efficient in adsorbing active components from PPE

Table 3

Correlation coefficients of kinetic models for ellagic acid released from BNC-PPE and o-BNC-PPE samples and corresponding release exponents.

		Correlation Coefficients (R^2)				n
		Zero-order	First-order	Higuchi	Korsmeyer-Peppas	
BNC-PPE	pH 1.2	0.6760	0.8120	0.8755	0.9913	0.2090
	pH 7.4	0.4220	0.6807	0.6595	0.9752	0.1150
o-BNC-PPE	pH 1.2	0.4866	0.7997	0.6986	0.7695	0.1125
	pH 7.4	0.6478	0.8410	0.8546	0.9768	0.1887

Fig. 4. Hydrolysis of punicalagin to produce ellagic acid.

Fig. 5. Antioxidant and hypoglycemic activities of BNC and o-BNC pomegranate formulations.

compared to pristine BNC suggesting the functionalization as a powerful tool to enhance the activity of BNC as carrier.

BNC-PPE contained only ellagic acid whereas o-BNC-PPE incorporated both, ellagic acid, and ellagitannins (punicalagin and punicalin). The release study indicated that the controlled release of ellagic acid, bioactive compound with limited absorption and a short elimination half-life, from o-BNC and BNC was successfully achieved, which could improve its bioavailability. The strong antioxidant activity was exhibited by both materials, with higher effect of o-BNC-PPE formulation, likely due to its richer chemical composition.

The hypoglycemic potential of both formulations was evaluated by in vitro analysis of anti- α -glucosidase activity. o-BNC-PPE formulation expressed stronger α -glucosidase inhibitory activity (IC_{50} 1.41 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) than BNC-PPE formulation (IC_{50} 29.09 $\mu\text{g/mL}$), following the same trend as in the antioxidant assays. The most important contribution of this investigation is that both formulations are significantly more effective in inhibition of α -glucosidase than standard drug acarbose, known α -glucosidase inhibitor (IC_{50} 156.64 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) making them potential candidates for new formulations using natural products in diabetes or impaired glucose tolerance management.

Although challenging, BNC and o-BNC manufacturing methods, including microbial cultivation, purification, and modification, are adaptable for larger-scale production. The BNC scale-up production are

extensively applied using both static and high volume bio-reactors (Chen et al., 2018; Shavyrkina et al., 2021). PPE extraction method presented in this study is not yet scalable to industrial levels, however the hydrodynamic cavitation-based extraction was effectively performed on a quasi-real scale (Benedetti et al., 2024). Ellagitannins in the PPE likely conjugate with pomegranate pectin, forming a stable, water-soluble compound with enhanced bioaccessibility. Future studies could explore the potential of complexing PPE with bacterial nanocellulose (BNC) or oxidized BNC (o-BNC) to further improve its effectiveness and bioavailability.

These novel BNC-based materials, enhanced with PPE phenolics, demonstrated significant potential as functional foods. They offer controlled release of bioactive compounds and health benefits that exceed those of traditional BNC-based foods, such as nata de coco, which, although structurally similar, lack the antioxidant and bioactive properties imparted by the inclusion of PPE.

Ethical statement – studies in humans and animals

All authors declare that all the experiments in the presented work was done as an in vitro studies and no studies carried out in humans and animals were performed.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Vuk Filipovic: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Jasmina Nikodinovic-Runic:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Katarina Savikin:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Jelena Zivkovic:** Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Jelena Mudric:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Nemanja Krgovic:** Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Marijana Ponjavic:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Investigation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.fufo.2025.100560](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fufo.2025.100560).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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